

DETAILED INVESTIGATION OF BONDED JOINTS FOR COMPOSITE REPAIRS

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1 Introduction

Repairs of composite structures in civil aircrafts should be often performed in “in field” conditions, which introduce severe restrictions in materials processing as compared to those used in a manufacturing plant (use of autoclave, moisture control of environment and components, drying methods, etc.). Bonded joints between the structure being repaired and the repair patch is the most critical part in terms of the strength and durability of the repair. The process involves producing a joint between a precured adherent and the uncured repair patch by means of a bonding agent (either an adhesive film or a laminating resin). The bonding agent and the repair patch are cured simultaneously. As a result, the interface between each adherent and the bonding agent is different, and consequently so is the strength.

This work presents an investigation on the fracture toughness (DCB specimens under mode I loading, G_{IC}) and fractography of bonded joints for composite repairs, trying to identify the failure modes and highlighting the differences between interfaces. It is shown that adhesive films produce tougher joints than laminating resins and that the failure modes and bond strength are different in both interfaces.

2 Experimental

The co-cured bonded joints were processed according to the sketch shown in Figure 1: plies of the un-cured material were placed on top of the tool, then the bonding agent was placed in between the un-cured plies and an already pre-cured panel, finally the bonded joint was cured in a furnace.

Fig. 1. Arrangement of pre-cured adherent, bonding agent and co-cured plies during the co-curing process.

Two different adhesive films, A1 and A2, and two laminating resins, L1 and L2, were used as bonding agents. In the case of joints bonded with adhesive films, a carbon plain weave fabric prepreg was used as adherent (193 g/m^2). The bonded joint (with the un-cured repair prepreg, adhesive film and pre-cured panel, according to Fig. 1) was cured in the same conditions as the pre-cured panel.

For the joints bonded with laminating resins, the adherent was a dry plain weave carbon fabric (193 g/m²) that was impregnated with laminating resins L1 and L2 by wet lay-up. In this case, fresh wet lay-up plies were co-bonded after applying a thin laminating resin layer. In all panels, a release film of 25 μm in thickness was placed in between the adherents to act as a pre-crack for Mode I delamination tests.

The mode I fracture toughness tests on double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens were performed according to the internal AIRBUS test method AITM1-0053 [3]. The test was performed by means of a 100 kN MTS Insight test machine with a 1kN load cell. In this test method, the mode I fracture toughness, G_{IC} , is calculated from the area integral under the load-displacement curve and the crack length increment.

A fluorescence optical microscope Leica DMR-XA was used to study failed zones at the edges of the specimen around the bond line after the completion of the mechanical test. The sample was prepared by cutting a piece of the specimen, including it in an epoxy matrix and then grinding and polishing. Fluorescence mode was used to enhance contrast between the matrix, fibres and the adhesive.

Figure 2. Comparison of the images of obtained by optical microscopy of one of the adherents after testing. The image on the left was obtained by episcopic conventional illumination. The image on the right was acquired in fluorescence mode. The image on the right permits to distinguish the adhesive from the resin wrested from the other adherent.

3 Results

The mode I fracture toughness at room temperature determined for the different combinations of bonding agents and adherents is shown in figure 3. It should be noticed the higher strength of adhesive films in spite of the fact that they have been

processed in out-of-autoclave conditions (their ideal processing would involve curing in autoclave).

Fig. 3. Fracture toughness of bonded joints prepared with adhesive films and laminating resins

The fracture toughness for adhesive films was three to four times larger than for laminating resins. Average G_{IC} for A1 and A2 batches were 673.7 and 757.8 J/m² respectively whereas for L1 and L2 lower values were obtained: 199.3 and 243.7 J/m².

The fracture surfaces of the tested specimens were first inspected by macrophotography, and then observed in the fluorescence microscope.

For the specimens joined with adhesive films there are three possible failure locations: i) at one of the interfaces between the adhesive and the adherents, either the pre-cured or the co-cured panel (adhesive failure), ii) through the adhesive (cohesive failure), and iii) in the adherent itself (if a complete layer of the adherent is pulled apart, this failure mode may be associated to a delamination).

Adhesive failure is the most undesirable failure mode as it is often related to an inadequate surface preparation of the adherents and/or the presence of contaminants. It may even lead to virtually null load capability of the bond (kissing bonds). On the contrary, bonds in which the adhesive and the interface remain undamaged, failure is located in the adherents, imply that the adhesive joint does not weaken the structure with respect to the load capability of the components being bonded [1].

This study revealed that in the specimens tested there were basically two different failure modes: i)

the matrix in the pre-cured adherent failed while the adhesive layer remained intact (fig. 4); ii) the adhesive failed cohesively near the interface of the co-cured adherent [2]. It should be emphasized that in neither case a pure adhesive failure was observed.

Fig. 4. Microphotography of a fractured specimen of a bonded joint with adhesive film. The pre-cured adherent appears on top of the image and the adhesive film and co-cured adherent on the bottom. As a general trend, the load displacement curves in samples with laminating resins were more heterogeneous than in samples bonded with adhesive films.

After the test, the arms of tested specimens were split apart to allow for the inspection of the fractured surface by macrophotography. The purpose of this was to study the failure mode of these specimens and see whether that affects the fracture toughness.

The analysis of the macrophotographies permitted the quantification of the areas attributable to each failure mode. For each batch, the relation between the failed area for a specific failure mode and the fracture toughness, demonstrated that the fracture toughness of each failure mode is different. The fracture toughness related to the cohesive failure of the adhesive near the co-bonded interface was about 800 J/m^2 for both adhesive films, whereas the failure of the pre-cured matrix was about 550 J/m^2 .

Fig 5. Macrophotography of the failed adherents after mode I testing. The upper panel is pre-cured and the lower panel co-cured. Pictures such as this were used in calculating the area fraction, as sketched in figure 6.

Fig. 6. Sketch of the method used to calculate the failed area fraction contributing to each failure mode.

In joints with laminating resins, a very thin layer of resin could be seen in the image obtained by optical microscopy (Fig. 7). The thickness of the resulting resin layer was small and dependent on the area of the samples (where the yarns of both adherents coincided the layer was thinner). It was not possible to elucidate whether the matrix of the pre-cured adherent or the resin from the co-cure adherent had failed.

In the case of figure 7, the failure consisted in the resin of the pre-cured adherent being pulled apart.

Fig. 7. Inspection of a failed joint with laminating resin by means of optical microscopy.

For bonded joints with laminating resins, the most remarkably microstructural trend is the presence of air bubbles periodically distributed as shown in figures 8 and 9. The size of these bubbles was determined by means of an image processing software over a set of pictures of each specimen.

Fig. 8. Stereoscopic view of the failed surface of bonded joint produced by means of a laminating resin.

Figure 9. SEM observation of a failed surface in joints produced with laminating resin.

4 Conclusions

This study shows that adhesive films produce bonded joints with larger fracture toughness than laminating resins. It is shown that, for adhesive films, the adhesion of the adhesive to both co-cured and pre-cured adherents is excellent and that the adhesive itself does not fail. Instead, the matrix of the pre-cured adherent is the weakest component of this system.

The scenario in joints with laminating resins is unclear due to the inability to identify where does failure occurs. The lack of a resin layer and the impossibility to distinguish the matrix of the pre-cured adherent from that of the co-cured adherent prevents its identification. It was evidenced in this study that the adhesive films A1 and A2 processed in out-of-autoclave conditions, are more suitable for repair operations than the laminating resins studied (L1 and L2) in terms of mechanical performance under static loading.

The investigation on these adhesive films and laminating resins is on-going with tests on samples in hot/wet conditions, fatigue tests and by the analysis of the results using other techniques as non-destructive inspection or the fractographic analysis.

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References

- [1] Davis M, Tomblin J. "*Best practice in adhesive-bonded structures and repairs.*" Virginia: National Technical Information Services (NTIS); 2007 April. Report No.: DOT/FAA/AR-TN06/57.
- [2] Costa J, Mahdi S, Renart J, Álvarez JM, de la Torre MA, Rodriguez-Bellido A. "*Quality assessment of bonded joints for repair purposes with adhesive films and laminating resins.*"
- [3] AITM-0053. "*AITM airbus test method carbon fibre reinforced plastics determination of fracture toughness energy of bonded joints mode I GIC.*" France: Airbus S.A.S; 2006 May. Report No.: AITM1-0053.